

THE CONCEPT OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARY LAW AND ITS FUNCTIONS.

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Xalqaro gumanitar huquq - qurolli mojarolar davrida qo'llaniladigan, qurolli kurash olib borishning ma'lum usullari va vositalarini qo'llashni ta'qiqlovchi yoki cheklovchi, bunday kurashlar davomida inson huquqlarini ta'minlovchi va ular buzilganligi uchun xalqaro-huquqiy javobgarlikni belgilovchi yuridik normalar va tamoyillar tizimidir.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquq tushunchasi o'zida ahloqiy va huquqiy atamalarni birlashtirgan. Agar «gumanizm» tushunchasiga ta'rif beradigan bo'lsak, u lotincha humanus degan so'zdan kelib chiqib, insoniy humanitas - insoniylik ma'nolarini anglatadi. Gumanizm adolatlilik, tenglik, insonning asosiy huquqlari va erkinliklariga rioya qilish hamda ularni hurmatlashni nazarda tutadi. Bir so'z bilan aytish mumkinki, gumanizm - insonni sevishdir. Lekin ming afsuslar bo'lsinkim, insoniyat taraqqiyotining butun tarixi mobaynida «gumanizm» tushunchasi hamisha o'ziga teskari bo'lgan barbaricus - yovuzlik, vahshiylik singari tushuncha bilan yonma-yon kelayotir. Hozirgi kunimizda ham bu ikki tushunchaning yonma-yon kelishi hollari hamon uchramoqda.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquq - xalqaro huquqning muhim qismlaridan hisoblanib, insoniylik tuyg'ulariga da'vatlaydi va urush vaqtida inson himoyasini ta'minlashga intiladi. Ushbu atamani mashhur huquqshunos olim Jan Pikte, tabiatan ikki xil, ya'ni huquqiy va ahloqiy kategoriyalarni qamrab olaid va aynan axloq normalari xalqaro huquqqa odob tushunchalarini olib kirishi ko'p hollarda insonparvarlik bilan bog'liqdir, deb ta'rif beradi. Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning o'ziga xos tomoni shundan iboratki, u faqatgina harbiy harakatlar davrida qo'llaniladi, chunki urush inson huquqlarin amalga oshirishga to'sqinlik qilishi yoki ularni jiddiy ravishda cheklab qo'yadi. Gumanitar huquq faqat qurolli ziddiyatlar vaqtida amal qilib, urush vaqtida uning qullanilishini cheklovchi moddalarga egadir. Bundan tashqari inson huquqlari to'g'risidagi qonun hujjatlari davlat va uning fuqarolari munosabatlarini, gumanitar huquq esa, davlat va dushman davlat fuqarolari o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni tartibga soladi .

Hozirgi kunda dunyoning turli mintaqalarida davom etayotgan turli ko'rinishdagi qurolli mojarolar butun insoniyatni tashvishlantirmoqda va bunday to'qnashuvlar insoniyat taraqqiyotiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Agar bu holatni aniq sonlarda ko'radigan bo'lsak, yanada dahshatliroq namoyon bo'ladi. SHveytsariyalik olim Jan Jak Babelning hisob-kitobiga qaraganda, keyingi 5500 yil ichida Yer kurrasida deyarli 14,5 ming katta va kichik urushlar bo'lib, ularda 3640 milliard kishi halok bulib ketgan. Faqat Ikkinchi jahon urushidan keyingina sayyoramizda 200 tadan ko'proq to'qnashuvlar yuz berdi va ularda 70 milliondan ko'proq kishi halok bo'ldi. Biz bu yerda ikkinchi jahon urushi 1945 yil tugaganini xotirlasak, so'nggi 57 yil ichida yiliga taxminan 1,3 million kishi faqatgina urushlar tufayli nobud bo'lmoqda. Bu ko'rsatkichlar hozirgi madaniyatli jamiyatimizdagi qora dog' emasmi?

Yuqorida tilga olingan qurolli to'qnashuvlar va ziddiyatlar o'zining ijtimoiy xarakteri va maqsadi bo'yicha davlatlararo, fuqarolik urushlarga, taqiqlanmagan bo'yicha mudofaa, milliy-ozodlik, BMT Ustaviga asosan tinchik o'rnatish uchun xarbiy aralashuvarga, taqiqlanganligi bo'yicha agressiv urushlar, urush aressiyasiga bo'lish mumkin.

XXI asrga kelib Butun jahon hamjamiyati inson omili oliy qadriyat ekanligini anglab yetib, bumasalaga jiddiy yondoshmoqda. Hozirgi kunda inson huquqlari masalasi davlat huquqi bilan tartibga solinibgina qolmay, balki Halqaro huquq normalari bilan tartibga solinmoqda.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning muhimligi va ahamiyati shundaki, u BMT Ustavida aytilganidek, davlatlarni «iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy, madaniy va gumanitar xarakterdagi xalqaro muammolarni hal etishda hamkorlikni amalga oshirish va inson huquqlariga hamda irqi, jinsi, tili va dinidan, qat'i nazar, hamma uchun asosiy erkinliklarga hurmatni qo'llab quvvatlash va rivojlantirishga» chaqiradi .

Bizga ma'lumki, hozirgi zamon jahon konstitutsiyalarida eng oliy qadriyat sifatida davlat va ijtimoiy tizim emas, balki inson olinadi. Xalqaro huquqda ham inson omiliga oliy qadriyat sifatida qaraladi.

Ikkinchi jahon urushi tugashi BMTning tuzilishi va 1948 yilda Inson Huquqlari Umumjahon Deklaratsiyasining qabul qilinishi inson huquqlarining rivojlanishida yangi davr bo'ldi. Halqaro huquqning asosiy printsiplaridan biri "inson huquqlarini hurmat qilish" printsipidir.

Inson huquqlari, gumanitar huquq bu ikki atama g'oyalarida bitta tarixiy va falsafiy asos bor: ikkala g'oya ham insonni yovuz kuchlardan muhofaza qilish zarurati paydo bo'lgan. O'tmishning og'ir davrlarida dunyoga keldi. Birir urush kulfatlari ta'sirini cheklashga intilish bilan izohlansa, boshqasi insonni har qanday qonunga xilof o'zboshimchalikdan himoyalashdir.

Albatta, inson huquqlari instituti nisbatan umumiy bo'lgan printsiplarni muxrlasa, gumunitar huquq o'ziga xos xarakterga ega bo'lib, ya'ni urush inson huquqlarini bajarishga xalaqit bera boshlaganda yoki ularni cheklaganda amal qila boshlaydi.

Bu turli huquqiy normalarning ikki xil yig'indisidir. Agar gumanitar huquq qurolli mojarolar vaqtida amalda bo'lsa, inson huquqlari to'g'risidagi normalar asosan tinchlik sharoitida o'zining ifodasini topadi va bu institutning vositalari urush holatida ba'zi bir cheklangan izohlarni belgilash bilan kifoyalanadi. Bundan tashqari, inson huquqlari to'g'risidagi normalar, eng avvalo, davlat bilan uning fuqarosi o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni, gumanitar huquq esa – davlat bilan dushman tomonning fuqarosi o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, biz so'z yuritayotgan mazkur ikki normalar sistemasi biri-biriga yaqin bo'lib, aynan bir paytda turlichadir. Ular bir-birini to'ldirib turadi.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning xalqaro huquqning mustaqil sohasi sifatida:

Birinchi, qurolli ixtiloflarda ishtirok etuvchilar o'tasidagi va xalqaro huquq sub'ektlari tomonidan qurolli kurash olib borish vositalari va usullari;

Ikkinchi, yaradorlarni, xarbiy asirlarni va tinch aholini himoya qilish sohasidagi munosabatlarni tartibga soladi;

Uchinchi, bu huquqlarni buzganlik uchun davlatlarning va ayrim shahslarning yuridik javobgarligini belgilaydi.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning maqsadi urushni taqiqlash bo'lmay, balki iloji boricha maksimal darajada urushning shafqatsiz oqibatlarini yengillashtirish, unda jafo ko'rganlarga kafolatlangan himoya va yordam ko'rsatishdir. Gumanitar huquqning alohidaligi yana shu bilan arakterlanadiki, u muayyan qurolli mojarolar davrida, una jafo ko'rganlar uchun huquqiy muhofaza aruriyati tug'ilgan vaqtda vujudga keladi va ushbu qurolli mojarolar bilan bog'liq holda harakatga tushadi. SHu bilan bira urush va qonun bir-biriga zid keluvchi tushunchalardir, degan fikrni inkor etadi .

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning normalari imperativ (jus cogens) xarakterni kasb etadi va unga amal qilish majburiy hisoblanadi.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning roli, qurolli mojarolar xalqaro xarakterga egami, yoki xalqaro bo'lmagan xarakterga ega bo'lishidan qat'iy nazar, uning jabrdiydasiga aylangan xar qanday shahsga gumanitar yordam ko'rsatishdan iborat hisoblanadi.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning predmeti.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning tartibga solish predmeti quyidagi davlatlararo munosabatlardir:

- Urushning boshlanishi;
- Urushda qatnashmayotgan davlatlarning betarafligi;
- Kurashayotgan taraflarning urushni olib borish usullarini cheklash;
- Urushda jafo ko'rganlarni himoya qilish;
- Urush davrida madaniy yodgorliklarni himoya qilish;
- «Harbiy harakatlarini tugashi» harbiy okkupatsiya rejimi;
- urushning tugatilishi;
- huquq buzilishi uchun davlatlarning javobgarligi;
- qurolli mojarolar huquqi normalarini buzganligi uchun jismoniy shahslarning jinoiy javobgarligi va boshqalardir.

Xalqaro huquqning amaldagi normalari xalqaro qurolli ziddiyatlarga ham, xalqaro maqomga ega bo'lmagan qurolli ziddiyatlarga ham ta'lluqlidir.

Xalqaro gumanitar huquqning tartibga solish predmeti quyidagi davlatlararo munosabatlardir:

Xalqaro qurolli ziddiyatlarga davlatlar o'rtasidagi qurolli to'qnashuvlar, mustamlakachilik tuzumi va chet el bosqinchilari hamda irqiy rejimlarga qarshi o'z mustaqilliklari uchun olib boradigan to'qnashuvlar kiradi. Ushbu huquq BMT Ustavi hamda boshqa xalqaro-huquqiy xujjatlarda o'z aksini topgan.

Xalqaro maqomga ega bo'lmagan qurolli ziddiyatlarga hukumat qo'shinlari va hukumatga qarshi bo'lgan qurolli guruhlar yoki fuqarolik urushi davridagi qurolli guruhlar o'rtasidagi to'qnashuvlar kiradi.

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